

Self-Sovereign-Identity Management and On-Boarding Framework for UAV Swarm Environment

Tafseer Akhtar¹, Christos Tselios², Polyxeni Nakou² and Ilias Politis¹

¹*Industrial Systems Institute, ATHENA Research Center*

{akhtar, politis}@athenarc.gr

²*Enebula BV, Amsterdam, Netherlands*

{c.tselios, p.nakou}@enebula.nl

Abstract—Traditional UAV authentication mechanisms rely on centralized architectures, which introduce risk of single points of failure and computationally intensive processes. To address these limitations, we propose a blockchain-based distributed authentication and on-boarding framework that decentralizes credential control, enabling user-centric management. This approach is particularly critical for UAV swarm environment, where high mobility disrupts communication stability and degrades authentication performance. Our framework integrates Hyperledger Identus as a cloud agent, KeyCloak for authorization, and NVIDIA Jetson for edge-device operations, establishing a resilient attribute-based authentication system. By leveraging selective attribute disclosure without exposing raw data, the solution aligns with Self-Sovereign Identity principles and privacy-by-design mandates. This eliminates dependence on central authorities while ensuring compliance with evolving security standards.

Index Terms—UAV-Swarm, Self-Sovereign-Identity, Hyperledger Identus, KeyCloak.

I. INTRODUCTION

User authentication is a critical requirement for data processors to secure personally identifiable information (PII) under GDPR [1], which mandates technical measures to ensure data security, implementing multi-factor authentication (MFA) can reduce unauthorized access risks, aligning with its accountability principle. Unmanned aerial vehicles (UAVs), commonly known as drones, have emerged as a transformative technology in modern aviation due to their unique capabilities: high-resolution data sensing, real-time processing, rapid deployment, mobility in challenging environments, and cost-efficiency. These attributes enable UAVs to revolutionize location-based applications across industries (e.g., Logistics, Telecommunications) [2]. UAV swarms leverage advanced sensor technologies (e.g., LiDAR, multispectral imaging) to enable high-precision, automated operations in applications such as environmental monitoring, disaster response, and precision agriculture [2]. These swarms operate via a hierarchical communication framework: as control center (CC) coordinates the swarm by transmitting commands to cluster heads. Cluster head

(H) acts as a relay between the CC and its cluster. Head aggregates sensor data from Member UAVs and forwards commands from the CC to the cluster. Member UAVs (M) execute tasks within the cluster and communicate exclusively through the H to minimize network congestion. This architecture ensures efficient swarm coordination, scalability, and redundancy [3]. UAVs have seen rapid technological advancements over the past decade, yet critical challenges remain unresolved prior to widespread deployment [2]. For instance, in edge computing (EC) enabled UAV systems, positioning UAVs closer to end-users significantly enhances service quality (e.g., ultra-low latency for real-time analytics). However, this proximity also amplifies exposure to cybersecurity threats that can compromise communication integrity. Malicious actors may exploit unprotected data streams to launch attacks such as: man-in-the-middle (MITM) attacks, replay attacks and data tampering. Mitigating these risks requires robust safeguards, such as blockchain-based authentication, lightweight cryptographic protocols tailored for UAV resource constraints [4]. UAV systems are vulnerable to different primary exploitation [4] vectors such as:

Data Exfiltration: Malicious actors intercept unencrypted communications to steal sensitive information. *Operational Sabotage:* Adversaries jam signals or spoof UAV controls to disrupt navigation, leading to collisions or mission failure. *System Compromise:* Corrupted firmware updates or phishing attacks allow malware injection, enabling attackers to hijack UAV clusters.

Authentication and authorization are foundational security requirements for UAV swarm deployments, ensuring only trusted devices can join the network and access mission-critical resources [5]. To achieve this, two core principles must be enforced: *Pre-Deployment Authentication:* Each UAV must undergo rigorous identity verification before joining the swarm. *Continuous Authorization:* Due to the dynamic nature of UAV networks where devices frequently enter/exit clusters or switch

roles periodic re-authentication is essential to confirm devices remain compliant with operational policies [6]. The unsecured operational environments of UAV swarms expose them to node capture attacks, where adversaries physically seize UAVs to extract cryptographic keys, sensor data, or control credentials. Compromised nodes can then impersonate legitimate UAVs, escalate privileges, or infiltrate the control center to access mission-critical secrets. These risks are exacerbated by UAVs' inherent constraints such as, limited computational powers, memory restrictions and energy efficiency demands. Identity registration systems are critical for securing UAV swarms, enabling unique device identification and role-based access control. However, these systems face few key challenges like, forged identities, insider misuse and cyber-attacks exploiting identity systems. Self Sovereign Identity (SSI) and Blockchain offer a transformative framework to address UAV security, privacy, and regulatory compliance challenges, by using SSI for decentralized identity management through

Decentralized Identifiers (DIDs): Each UAV is assigned a unique, cryptographically verifiable DID stored on the blockchain, eliminating reliance on centralized authorities. *Verifiable Credentials (VCs)*: Operators issue VCs to authorize UAVs for specific tasks. *User Control*: Operators/UAVs own and manage their identities, sharing only minimal data and Blockchain for immutable logging and transparency through: *Tamper-Proof Flight Logs*: Every UAV action is hashed and recorded on a permissioned blockchain (e.g., Hyperledger Identities), ensuring auditability. *Real-Time Traceability*: Authorities can trace unauthorized flights or policy violations via transparent, time-stamped records. *Smart Contracts*: Automate compliance checks. *Zero-Knowledge Proofs (ZKPs)*: Allow entities to prove the validity of a credential without revealing sensitive details [7].

Figure 1 illustrates the proposed system architecture, the workflow comprises three core phases issuance, presentation, and verification as detailed in the design section. This work provides a privacy-preserving, attribute-based authentication framework for UAV swarms by integrating SSI, ZKPs and Selective Disclosure JSON Web Tokens (SD-JWT). Leveraging Hyperledger Identities (for decentralized identity management) and KeyCloak (for federated access control) [8], the framework addresses UAV onboarding, role-based authorization, and our key contributions are:

- An integrated SSI with Blockchain system framework is proposed using HI, KeyCloak and Jetson for edge-based UAV swarm.
- This framework empowers the control center (CC) to seamlessly onboard and authenticate UAVs within a transparent swarm environment, ensuring secure integration and real-time operational oversight without disrupting swarm cohesion.

II. STATE OF THE ART

Non-blockchain-based authentication systems lack a decentralized platform to securely store and share UAV registration

Fig. 1: UAV Authentication flow in SSI framework

and authentication data. In this work [9] authors introduced a blockchain-based decentralized authentication framework for industrial UAVs. Their system leverages self-executing smart contracts to autonomously manage secure authentication and data exchange processes, enabling UAVs to update or access critical operational information while ensuring transparency and immutability across the network. Study [10] explored blockchain's role in enhancing cybersecurity for industrial UAVs, including a performance evaluation of Hyperledger Fabric, a modular, enterprise-grade blockchain framework, for securing UAV networks, similar on this, [11] demonstrated how blockchain-based security mechanisms can upgrade authentication protocols and streamline trust management in UAV swarms, specifically through decentralized, tamper-evident ledger systems that strengthen mutual authentication and dynamic cluster coordination. Study [12] proposed a blockchain-assisted framework for secure group communication in UAV networks, leveraging distributed ledger technology to automate key distribution and immutably log communication events. Nevertheless, the framework overlooks, hardware-rooted security and location-aware dynamic clustering to optimize swarm coordination. The work [3], used the blockchain for authentication and intelligent swarm clustering, by utilizing hardware-rooted security for two-way mutual authentication.

Current research lacks robust decentralized authentication and authorization frameworks tailored for UAV swarms, particularly those integrating hardware-rooted security and adaptive coordination mechanisms. Blockchain technology offers a promising solution by enabling tamper-resistant, distributed management of UAV security credentials, ensuring data integrity and trust across dynamic swarm operations. However, existing approaches fall short in enhancing blockchain-based authentication/authorization with hardware-level uniqueness and tamper detection with incorporating location-aware clustering to optimize swarm coordination while maintaining decentralized trust.

III. DESIGN

Hyperledger Indentus (HI) features allow developers to use the cloud agent for creating a secure UAV swarm network where it consists of control centers, cluster heads UAVs, and members UAVs. A blockchain-integrated UAV swarm network can enforce granular role-based permissions by assigning cryptographically signed credentials to participants. For example: *Holder Certificates*: Restrict drones to communication within their designated swarm and with the control center, preventing unauthorized interactions with external UAVs or networks. *Verifier/Issuer Certificates*: Grant the CC elevated privileges, enabling it to create and authenticate identities and orchestrate cross-swarm coordination. This tiered identity framework ensures tamper-resistant segregation of duties, aligning access rights with operational roles while preserving the decentralized trust model inherent to blockchain systems. HI mandates that all network identities be cryptographically verifiable and issued exclusively by a trusted Certificate Authority (CA). HI integrates a dedicated CA with a private root certificate, enabling it to securely generate, distribute, and manage digital identities and certificates, aligning with enterprise-grade security standards [13].

In HI blockchain networks, peers are responsible for maintaining the distributed ledger that govern network operations. However, in UAV swarm environments, designating mobile drones as peers is impractical due to their dynamic mobility, limited computational resources, and intermittent connectivity factors that destabilize consensus mechanisms and increase latency. To mitigate this, the control center serves as the sole peer node, centralizing blockchain management while retaining decentralized trust. A Verifiable Credential (VC), as defined in [14], is a cryptographically secured, tamper-evident credential whose authorship and integrity can be independently authenticated. The World Wide Web Consortium (W3C) also outlines a non-normative lifecycle for VCs, providing a flexible framework for issuance, storage, presentation, and revocation. This lifecycle shares structural and functional parallels with the SSI model, particularly in its adoption of standardized roles, issuer, holder, and verifier which form the foundation of decentralized SSI ecosystems. VCs rely on tamper-evident metadata such as cryptographic verification keys, stored within a Verifiable Data Registry (VDR), a decentralized ledger that enforces strict integrity and role-based access control. To ensure authenticity, VCs are cryptographically signed by the issuer, binding the credential's content to their identity.

A. Credentials Management

Aligned with the W3C-compliant data model [14], a VC comprises three core components, *Credential Metadata*: Contextual data, *Claims*: Structured assertions (key-value pairs) describing the subject's attributes and *Proof(s)*: Cryptographic signatures or zero-knowledge evidence validating authenticity and integrity. A VDR a decentralized ledger or blockchain

serves as the trust anchor, storing DIDs, schemas, and revocation lists to ensure global resolvability and auditability. Within this framework, three roles interact with the VDR at distinct stages:

- **Issuer (CC)**: Embeds proofs into credentials and publishes schemas to the VDR.
- **Holder (UAV)**: Requests, stores, and selectively discloses credentials via verifiable presentations.
- **Verifier (CC)**: Queries the VDR to validate credential status and schema compliance.

The VC lifecycle is governed by three interdependent phases:

- 1) **Issuing**: Issuing phase governs the generation of VCs, cryptographically binding claims to a subject while embedding tamper-evident proofs. Authorized issuers utilize either newly defined schemas or existing ones, stored in a VDR. This work adopts JSON for its widespread interoperability and alignment with industry standards. Each credential adheres to a predefined context, a structured template specifying mandatory fields (e.g., issuer DID, issuance date, credential schema) that must be populated to ensure semantic consistency and validity during verification. The holder retains the cryptographically signed VC within a secure digital wallet, ensuring end-to-end encryption and tamper-proof storage until its selective disclosure during verification workflows.
- 2) **Presentation**: Presentation phase requires user-centric transparency, the holder retains full visibility into which attributes, a verifier requests and explicitly consents to their selective disclosure. To strengthen privacy, the system integrates ZKPs, cryptographic primitives that enable holders to validate claims without revealing raw data. This minimizes information leakage while ensuring compliance with verifier requirements a cornerstone of SSI. By embedding ZKPs into attribute-based authentication frameworks, the solution not only enhances user control over personal data but also mitigates risks of credential misuse or unintended correlation across transactions, advancing trust in decentralized ecosystems.
- 3) **Verification**: During the verification phase, the verifier cryptographically validates the integrity, authenticity, and revocation status of a presented VC. Critically, this process operates without direct issuer-verifier interaction, as the proposed SSI framework eliminates dependence on centralized intermediaries. Instead, trust is anchored in cryptographic proofs and decentralized registries, such as a VDR, which stores schemas, issuer public keys, and revocation lists. By querying the VDR, verifiers autonomously confirm credential validity while preserving user control over identity data.

This architecture ensures end-to-end trust while adhering to SSI principles of user control and minimal disclosure.

Fig. 2: UAV On-Boarding

B. On-Boarding

The onboarding process for a new UAV is illustrated in Figure 2. In the first stage (Figure 2a), the UAV undergoes credential creation, as outlined in the credential management section. Once the credential is generated, it is stored in the UAV’s wallet. The UAV then interacts with KeyCloak for authorization, only after successful authentication does it proceed to the next phase. The control center (CC), serving a dual role as both issuer and verifier, subsequently initiates credential verification for the newly authorized UAV. This verification process follows the steps detailed in the credential management section. Upon successful verification, the UAV is assigned to the swarm based on the location of its designated cluster head (H), as depicted in Figure 2b.

IV. IMPLEMENTATION

A. Hyperledger Identus Cloud Agent

HI seamlessly integrated with the Identus Wallet to enable secure, user-governed credential storage and privacy-preserving data sharing. The framework natively supports SD-JWT-VC, a W3C-aligned protocol that empowers users to cryptographically prove specific credential attributes (e.g., Model_Id, MAC_Addr) without disclosing extraneous personal data, ensuring compliance with zero-trust and minimal disclosure principles. In this framework, holder of credential is UAV (H) and credential’s issuer and verifier is control center (CC). The operations of the SSI system using HI are described below:

- 1. Schema Registration:** In decentralized identity frameworks,

the issuer first publish a DID schema to Cardano to establish the governance rules, data structure, and permissible attributes for DIDs. This schema acts as a template, ensuring consistency and interoperability across all DID documents subsequently registered by holders. By anchoring the schema to Cardano, the system guarantees that every DID document adheres to predefined standards, enabling secure and machine-readable identity management across distributed networks.

- 2. Registration:** To register a decentralized identity, a holder is first connected to an identity network anchored on the Cardano, a proof-of-stake ledger designed for scalability and security. The holder then authenticated with a trusted issuer to obtain a Peer-to-Peer Decentralized Identifier (PDID), a cryptographically secured identifier that facilitates direct, intermediary-free communication between network participants. By binding the PDID to Cardano, system ensures immutability and auditability, enabling secure, tamper-resistant interactions within the decentralized ecosystem.

- 3. Establishing Connection:** The PDID enables a cryptographically authenticated communication channel between issuer (CC) and holder (UAV), leveraging Cardano to enforce mutual trust, data integrity, and tamper-resistant interactions.

- 4. Signed Attributes:** Holder (UAV) cryptographically signs a subset of their identity attributes using a private key and submits them to the issuer (CC). Leveraging a privacy-preserving protocol, the issuer generates a blinded identity token. This token enables the holder to authenticate transactions or access services without exposing raw attributes, balancing verifiable

trust with minimal disclosure principles.

5. Credential Generation: Using the holder's submitted attributes, the issuer constructs a blinded identity token then, it signs the blinded token with their private key, which is cryptographically linked to their DID registered on Cardano. This binds issuer's identity to the credential, ensuring non-repudiation. Creates a unique public-private key pair for the holder, enabling secure future interactions and transmits the final credential, containing the blinded attributes, issuer's signature, and holder's public key via an encrypted channel.

6. Credential Storage in Wallet: Holder (UAV) receives the sent credential from issuer (cc) and stores it securely in the HI wallet.

7. Issuer's Presence: Issuer (CC) publishes a DID and its associated DID Doc to Cardano. The DID Document serves as a machine-readable identity profile, containing, contextual information, public keys for authentication, encryption, and digital signatures and credential Schema (registered on the Cardano) that enforces structural and semantic consistency for credentials issued under the DID.

Verification Presentation: The holder (UAV) constructs a ZKP based credential presentation, cryptographically attesting to specific claims without disclosing raw attribute values. A credential presentation leverage selective disclosure to share only role-based permissions while withholding sensitive data.

Verifier Verification: The Verifier (CC) ensures the proof's authenticity and compliance through a two-step validation process: The Verifier uses the Issuer's public key, securely retrieved from Cardano, to validate the digital signature embedded in the proof. This confirms the credential was legitimately issued and remains untampered. The verifier also cross-references the Cardano to verify the credential's current status and adherence to predefined schema, ensuring alignment with governance rules and operational standards.

For seamless authentication in SSI system we used:

SD-JWT Mechanisms: We used JSON Web Token (JWT) validation middleware on the server-side to authenticate stateless, cryptographically signed session tokens. This involves: signature verification by validating tokens using a preconfigured public key or HMAC secret to ensure integrity and authenticity. Claims validation through enforcing token expiration, issuer, and audience checks to prevent replay attacks or unauthorized access. Stateless session management by decoding and trust token payloads without relying on server-side session storage, enhancing scalability.

Exposed APIs: We used Keycloak Connect-compliant endpoints to streamline credential negotiation and cryptographic proof-of-possession workflows, adhering to OAuth2/OIDC specifications. By using:

- `auth/request`: Initiates a proof challenge by returning a time-bound, non-reusable cryptographic nonce to authenticate client requests.
- `auth/verify`: Validates submitted proofs and issues

short-lived access/refresh tokens upon successful verification.

Ensure these endpoints enforce mutual TLS (mTLS), validate `client_id` and `redirect_uri` parameters, and integrate with Keycloak's identity provider (IdP) for centralized policy enforcement. This aligns with Keycloak's token exchange and identity brokering capabilities, enabling secure, standards-driven authentication in distributed systems.

B. KeyCloak and Jetson Nano

We used KeyCloak as authorization/authentication agent for all participants (Issuer, Holder, Verifier), Keycloak served as the centralized IdP within the framework, streamlining authentication, authorization, and secure token management for all participants (*issuer, holders, and verifier*). Its core functions include:

1) Unified Authentication:

- Managed login workflows for users and system agents, enforcing multi-factor authentication (MFA) for high-risk operations.
- Issued JWTs to authenticate participants, embedding role-specific claims and permissions.

2) Realm-Based Access Control:

- Segregated participants into dedicated realms to enforce role-based policies and isolate sensitive operations.
- Configured fine-grained permissions to restrict API access.

3) Token Lifecycle Management:

- Signed JWTs using RSA-256/EdDSA keys, with issuer public keys registered in the Cardano.

By acting as a policy orchestration layer, Keycloak bridged centralized security governance with decentralized identity principles, ensuring compliance without sacrificing scalability.

We deployed the HI framework on an NVIDIA Jetson Nano Developer Kit, running on Ubuntu 18.04 LTS and linked with s-500 drone, which is optimized for edge computing in UAV swarm environments. This deployment enables:

- 1) **On-Device VC Issuance:** Leveraged the Jetson Nano's GPU-accelerated cryptography (CUDA cores), HI generates and signs W3C-compliant credentials with hardware-backed keys, ensuring tamper-resistant identity attestation for swarm members.
- 2) **Decentralized Trust Anchors:** Each UAV acted as a Holder with a unique DID, registered on a Cardano for real-time, offline-first authentication.
- 3) **Interoperable Swarm Coordination:** Credentials enforced standardized role-based permissions across heterogeneous UAVs, enabling secure, cryptographically verifiable communication via protocols.

By pairing HI's DIDComm v2 messaging with the Jetson Nano's low-latency edge processing, this architecture achieves dynamic swarm authentication environments.

Fig. 3: SSI Framework's Initial Evaluation

C. Architecture and Roles

This architecture establishes cryptographically assured trust in decentralized credentials by integrating Keycloak as a policy-driven IdP with OAuth 2.0 and OIDC protocols.

In the proposed framework, the CC assumed the role of a credential issuer, utilizing the HI agent to cryptographically generate, sign, and issue VCs. These credentials encode role-specific permissions and are anchored to a Cardano to ensure tamper-evident provenance. The CC served a dual role as both Issuer and Verifier of credentials. Leveraging the HI agent, the CC cryptographically validates the authenticity and integrity of presented credentials, cross-referencing the Cardano to confirm revocation status and schema compliance. The HI agent, deployed as a cloud-native microservice, orchestrated secure, standards-compliant interactions between all participants. Every entity must first authenticate with KeyCloak, the centralized authorization server, to obtain a JWT access token scoped to its role. This token grants least-privilege access to the HI agent's APIs, enforcing role-based access control (RBAC) and cryptographic validation of actions.

While a comprehensive performance evaluation of the proposed framework is beyond the scope of this paper due to page restrictions, its operational efficiency is inherently tied to the capabilities of the underlying public permissioned blockchain, Cardano.

V. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In the proposed framework, we executed multiple sequential instances of the credential-creation process. For this purpose, an

NVIDIA Jetson developer kit interfaced with an S-500 platform was utilized. Due to hardware limitations and environmental constraints in the experimental setup, testing was limited to six UAVs.

In the figure 3, we evaluated performance outcomes for four core processes, credential creation, credential reception, proof creation, and proof reception. All results were quantified using two metrics, elapsed time and the sequential number of UAVs involved in each operation. Figure 3(a) quantifies the interaction time between the UAV (holder) and the Control Center (CC) during connection establishment. The CC first acts as an issuer, then transitions to a verifier role, requiring termination of the initial connection before re-establishing it. Figures 3(b) and 3(d) depict the credential creation time and proof creation time, respectively, while Figures 3(c) and 3(e) illustrate the credential reception time and proof reception time between the CC (issuer/verifier) and the UAV (holder).

VI. SECURITY ANALYSIS

In the proposed architecture, the HI cloud agent (operated by the control center,) interfaces with edge-resident wallets onboard UAVs via an HTTP-based communication channel compliant with HI standards. Within this framework: UAVs act as Holders, storing and managing their VCs in secure, hardware-protected wallets. The CC assumes a dual role as both Issuer (generating and signing VCs for UAV on-boarding) and Verifier (authenticating credentials). This design ensures seamless, standards-aligned interactions between the swarm and the CC, enabling decentralized trust while maintaining

centralized operational oversight. By adhering to HI specifications, the system guarantees cryptographic integrity and interoperability across HTTP transactions, even in resource-constrained edge environments. To counter spoofing attacks, HI framework secures inter-agent communication via DIDComm v2, a privacy-preserving messaging protocol that encapsulates payloads in end-to-end encrypted envelopes. These envelopes leverage cryptographic key-agreement mechanisms defined in DID Documents (DIDDocs), ensuring only authenticated parties with valid DIDs can decrypt or access sensitive data. For tampering attacks, HI employs blockchain's immutable ledger to log transactions and enforce message integrity. Every transmitted payload is cryptographically signed using the sender's private key, allowing recipients to verify authenticity and detect unauthorized modifications. This dual-layered approach, combining DIDComm's encrypted channels with blockchain-anchored signatures, ensures robust resistance to both impersonation and data manipulation in decentralized ecosystems. Attackers can only attempt to extract sensitive data by intercepting Presentation requests, structured queries specifying the attributes a verifier seeks. To thwart unauthorized disclosure, these requests are cryptographically signed by the verifier and countersigned by the holder using ZKPs or selective disclosure mechanisms. This dual-signature workflow ensures:

Verifier Authentication: The holder validates the verifier's identity via their digital signature, which is anchored to a DID registered on a verifiable data registry. *Tamper-Evident Consent:* The holder's countersignature cryptographically binds their consent to the requested attributes, ensuring no third party can alter the scope of disclosure. *Minimal Information Leakage:* Even if intercepted, the request reveals only the *existence* of required attributes not their values unless explicitly authorized by the holder. Replay attacks and repudiation risks are mitigated through DIDComm v2 Signed Envelopes, which cryptographically bind each credential presentation to a unique session challenge. In this workflow:

Mutual Authentication: The holder and verifier jointly sign the credential presentation using ephemeral session keys, ensuring the verifier cannot maliciously reuse credentials outside the authorized context.

Challenge-Response Integrity: A time-bound, non-reusable cryptographic challenge is embedded in the envelope, rendering intercepted presentations invalid for future transactions.

VII. CONCLUSIONS

We propose a decentralized SSI framework integrating HI and KeyCloak to enable attribute-based authentication and secure onboarding in UAV swarm environments. By adhering to W3C DID and VC standards, the framework decentralizes identity management, empowering users to control identity data locally, reducing reliance on centralized servers, and enhancing privacy and security through distributed governance. Furthermore, the framework is strategically positioned to integrate

with emerging technologies such as Web3 ecosystems and quantum computing. While these integrations pose technical and scalability challenges, they also unlock transformative opportunities for innovation in secure, decentralized identity management.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

This research is supported by the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme "REFINE" (GA No: 101129910) and "EUSOME" (GA No: 101187121).

REFERENCES

- [1] D. A. Tamburri, "Design principles for the general data protection regulation (gdpr): A formal concept analysis and its evaluation," *Information Systems*, vol. 91, p. 101469, 2020.
- [2] H. Shakhathreh, A. H. Sawalmeh, A. Al-Fuqaha, Z. Dou, E. Almaita, I. Khalil, N. S. Othman, A. Khreishah, and M. Guizani, "Unmanned aerial vehicles (uavs): A survey on civil applications and key research challenges," *Ieee Access*, vol. 7, pp. 48 572–48 634, 2019.
- [3] R. Karmakar, G. Kaddoum, and O. Akhrif, "A blockchain-based distributed and intelligent clustering-enabled authentication protocol for uav swarms," *IEEE Transactions on Mobile Computing*, vol. 23, no. 5, pp. 6178–6195, 2023.
- [4] J. Srinivas, A. K. Das, N. Kumar, and J. J. Rodrigues, "Tcalas: Temporal credential-based anonymous lightweight authentication scheme for internet of drones environment," *IEEE Transactions on Vehicular Technology*, vol. 68, no. 7, pp. 6903–6916, 2019.
- [5] D. Wang, P. Wang, C.-g. Ma, and Z. Chen, "Robust smart card based password authentication scheme against smart card security breach," *Cryptology ePrint Archive*, 2012.
- [6] G. Bansal and B. Sikdar, "S-maps: Scalable mutual authentication protocol for dynamic uav swarms," *IEEE Transactions on Vehicular Technology*, vol. 70, no. 11, pp. 12 088–12 100, 2021.
- [7] A. Mühle, A. Grüner, T. Gayvoronskaya, and C. Meinel, "A survey on essential components of a self-sovereign identity," *Computer Science Review*, vol. 30, pp. 80–86, 2018.
- [8] M. A. Christie, A. Bhandar, S. Nakandala, S. Marru, E. Abeyinghe, S. Pamidighantam, and M. E. Pierce, "Using keycloak for gateway authentication and authorization," 2017.
- [9] Y. Tan, J. Wang, J. Liu, and N. Kato, "Blockchain-assisted distributed and lightweight authentication service for industrial unmanned aerial vehicles," *IEEE Internet of Things Journal*, vol. 9, no. 18, pp. 16 928–16 940, 2022.
- [10] I. J. Jensen, D. F. Selvaraj, and P. Ranganathan, "Blockchain technology for networked swarms of unmanned aerial vehicles (uavs)," in *2019 IEEE 20th International Symposium on "A World of Wireless, Mobile and Multimedia Networks"(WoWMoM)*. IEEE, 2019, pp. 1–7.
- [11] S. Sahoo, A. K. Shukla, and H. Rana, "Future directions of uav swarm communications," in *2021 8th International Conference on Signal Processing and Integrated Networks (SPIN)*. IEEE, 2021, pp. 324–327.
- [12] K. Gai, Y. Wu, L. Zhu, K.-K. R. Choo, and B. Xiao, "Blockchain-enabled trustworthy group communications in uav networks," *IEEE Transactions on Intelligent Transportation Systems*, vol. 22, no. 7, pp. 4118–4130, 2020.
- [13] "Hyperledger foundation. identus," <https://www.lfdecentralizedtrust.org/projects/identus/> [Accessed: 25 February 2025].
- [14] N. Fotiou, Y. Thomas, G. Xylomenos, V. A. Siris, and G. C. Polyzos, "Authentication and authorization for content-centric routing using w3c dids and vcs," in *2022 IEEE Conference on Standards for Communications and Networking (CSCN)*. IEEE, 2022, pp. 163–168.